

The Stability of Beryllium Complexes with Organic Ligands. II. Amino Carboxylic Acids.

P. CHARAN DAS and G. S. RAO

Chemistry Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Bombay 85.

Manuscript received 20 June 1972; accepted 30 January 1973

The stability constants of complexes of beryllium with glycine, iminodiacetic acid, nitrilotriacetic acid and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid have been determined by pH titration method at 35° and an ionic strength of 0.1M. The stability constants of complexes of related metal ions—aluminium and magnesium with these ligands have also been determined under the above conditions for comparison. It is found that among the ions, the stability of the complexes increases as $Mg^{2+} < Be^{2+} < Al^{3+}$, which is expected from the variations in their charge and radii. The utility of log K -pK relationship as a diagnostic measure to find out the number of groups which are coordinated is examined. It is found that in the cases of ligands, nitrilotriacetic acid and ethylene diaminetetraacetic acid, the maximum number of groups coordinated are only three.

IN part. I of the series, the stability constants of beryllium complexes with salicylaldehyde and related ligands were reported¹. In the present study the stability constants of beryllium complexes with amino carboxylic acids—glycine, iminodiacetic acid (IMDA), nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) are reported.

The beryllium ion shows a weak coordinating tendency for nitrogen which is apparent from the fewer number of complexes formed even with O-N donors. Earlier results on the stability constants of beryllium complexes with glycine² and EDTA³ are conflicting while there is no data available on IMDA. The stability constant of beryllium-NTA complex has been determined by solvent extraction³. Glycine, IMDA, NTA and EDTA can function as bi, tri tetra and hexadentate ligands respectively. The small size and the coordination number "four" of beryllium are expected to show some interesting features in its behaviour with these polydentate ligands. The stability constants of complexes of magnesium and aluminium have also been determined for comparison as these metals are closely related to beryllium in their chemical properties.

Materials and Methods: All chemicals used in the experiments were of Analar grade. The ligands were recrystallized from water and the purity was checked from the concordance of pK values with those reported in literature⁴. A solution of beryllium chloride was prepared by dissolving beryllium hydroxide in hydrochloric acid and beryllium was estimated gravimetrically as oxide⁵. The free acid was estimated by passing an aliquot of the stock solution which contains excess acid through a cation exchanger in the H⁺ form. From the concentration of beryllium and the total acid liberated the free acid was calculated. The stock solution of EDTA was standardized by titrating with a standard solution of zinc sulphate⁵. Aluminium was estimated gravimetrically as 8-hydroxy quinolate⁵ and magnesium was estimated by titration with EDTA using eriochrome black T as an indicator⁵. Carbonate

free potassium hydroxide was prepared according to the method given by Albert and Serjeant⁶, and standardized.

Radiometer pH meter (PHM-4) having a reproducibility of ± 0.005 pH unit was used in the present studies. It was standardized by buffers of 0.05M potassium hydrogen phthalate and 0.01M borax before each experiment. The titrations were carried out in a cell provided with a jacket through which water was circulated from a thermostat maintained at 35°. Nitrogen gas free from carbon dioxide washed and presaturated with the solution to be titrated was passed through the cell during titrations to prevent the absorption of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. The titrations were carried out maintaining an ionic strength of 0.1M with potassium chloride. The solution was stirred by means of a magnetic stirrer during the titration. After each addition of alkali, pH reading was noted when a constant value was attained.

The hydrolysis correction in the beryllium systems was applied following the method developed by Nair⁷ and the free metal ion in the system was calculated using Newton's method of approximation⁸. The stability constants obtained after the hydrolysis correction are designated by K'_1 .

In the metal glycine systems, \bar{n} and pL were calculated by Irving-Rossotti method⁹. In the other systems, these were calculated using the titration data i.e., pH and 'a', where 'a' is the number of moles of alkali per mole of ligand. From the results of \bar{n} and pL , K_1 the stability constant was calculated by methods reported by Carini and Martell¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

The pK values of the ligands are given in table 1. The results show that the pK value of the least dissociable hydrogen increases as :

1. *Complexes of berylliums* : The results and the titration data for the beryllium complexes with different ligands are given in table 2 and the stability constants in Table 5.

TABLE 1—*pK* VALUES OF AMINOPOLYCARBOXYLIC ACIDS IN WATER AT 35° AND IONIC STRENGTH 0.1*M*

Ligand	<i>pK</i> ₁	<i>pK</i> ₂	<i>pK</i> ₃	<i>pK</i> ₄
Glycine	2.4	9.5	—	—
IMDA	2.62	9.23	—	—
NTA	1.85	2.69	9.72	—
EDTA	2.50	2.93	6.09	10.05

(i) *Glycine* : The titration was carried out at a ligand to metal ratio of 3.5. The calculated values of log *K*₁ and log *K*₂ were found to be 6.75 and 5.13 respectively. Log *K*'₁ (after hydrolysis correction) was found to be 6.4. Attempts to calculate hydrolytic correction for log *K*₂ resulted in erroneous values and therefore it is not reported. However, a value of 13.3 for log β₂ was reported by Perkins² who, however, pointed out that the values obtained for beryllium systems must be treated with caution as both its salts and complexes hydrolyse above *pH* 6, which makes it difficult to assess the complex formation on the alkaline side.

(ii) *IMDA* : The ratio of ligand to metal was kept at 1.0 for this ligand, NTA and EDTA since

they are expected to form only 1 : 1 complex. Log *K*₁ was found to be 7.2, while log *K*'₁ was 6.4. The *pK* value of IMDA is less than that of glycine but the stability constant is nearly the same as log *K*'₁ of glycine.

(iii) *NTA* : Log *K*₁ and log *K*'₁ were found to be 8.3 and 6.9. Stary³ reported log *K*₁ as 7.11±0.05. Compared to glycine and IMDA, *pK*₃ of NTA is the highest and it would be expected to form a complex whose stability is much higher than that of either IMDA or glycine.

(iv) *EDTA* : The stability constant was calculated in the region of 'α' between 3.5 and 3.7 where only BeL is supposed to form¹⁰. Log *K*₁ and log *K*'₁ were found to be 10.2 and 9.9 respectively. Stary³ reported a value of 9.27±0.03 while Bamberger and Botbol¹¹ gave 8.68±0.02, both values by solvent extraction. The results on this system obtained by various workers were reviewed by Bamberger and Laguna³ and found quite conflicting. However, the value of 9.9 obtained in the present study is of the same order as reported by Stary.

Correlation of stability constants with basicity of ligands : Schwarzenbach¹² correlated the stability of calcium complexes of a number of aminopolycarboxylic acids with the *pK* value of the least dissociable hydrogen of the ligand and found that the linear plots fall into three separate groups depending on whether the ligand is a tridentate or tetradentate and also on the number of rings in the chelate. Moeller and Thompson¹³ also observed a similar

TABLE 2—*pH* TITRATION DATA ON BERYLLIUM SYSTEMS.

Temperature = 35°, Ionic strength = 0.1*M*.

Glycine	<i>T</i> _M = 1.13 × 10 ⁻² <i>M</i>				<i>T</i> _L = 4 × 10 ⁻² <i>M</i>					
	<i>pH</i>									
<i>pH</i>	4.0	4.25	4.40	4.50	4.70	4.9	5.0			
\bar{n}	0.35	0.53	0.65	0.76	0.88	1.00	1.07			
<i>pL</i>	7.05	6.68	6.64	6.56	6.37	6.19	6.00			
<i>pH</i>	5.1	5.3	5.4	5.75						
\bar{n}	1.10	1.16	1.22	1.28						
<i>pL</i>	5.88	5.82	5.73	5.39						
IMDA	<i>T</i> _M = <i>T</i> _L = 1 × 10 ⁻² <i>M</i>									
<i>pH</i>	3.83	3.98	4.11	4.25	4.39	4.54	5.07	5.56		
\bar{n}	0.13	0.23	0.33	0.43	0.54	0.64	0.85	0.95		
<i>pL</i>	7.47	7.37	7.30	7.23	7.18	7.08	6.98	6.93		
NTA	<i>T</i> _M = 1.07 × 10 ⁻³ <i>M</i> ,				<i>T</i> _L = 1 × 10 ⁻³ <i>M</i>					
<i>pL</i>	3.68	3.94	4.39	4.67	5.08					
\bar{n}	0.03	0.13	0.34	0.52	0.79					
<i>pL</i>	9.05	8.84	8.52	8.39	8.44					
EDTA	<i>T</i> _M = 1.13 × 10 ⁻³ <i>M</i>				<i>T</i> _L = 1.01 × 10 ⁻³ <i>M</i>					
Volume	0.0	0.1	0.3	0.50	0.70	0.90	1.10	1.20	1.3	1.4
<i>a</i>	0.0	0.19	0.59	0.99	1.39	1.78	2.18	2.38	2.57	2.77
<i>pH</i>	2.85	2.89	2.98	3.10	3.26	3.50	3.91	4.13	4.30	4.44
Volume	1.50	1.60	1.70	1.80	1.90	2.00	2.10	2.20	2.30	
<i>a</i>	2.97	3.17	3.37	3.57	3.77	3.96	4.16	4.38	4.58	
<i>pH</i>	4.57	4.70	4.83	4.99	5.20	5.58	6.07	6.75	7.17	

correlation for the complexes of lanthanides with aminopolycarboxylic acids using ΣpK as the measure of basicity.

In the present study, Fig. 1 shows the correlation between $\log K'_1$ and ΣpK i.e., sum of the pK values of the ligand. Plot 1 depicts the correlation of $\log K'_1$ with ΣpK of the ligands, namely, IMDA, NTA and EDTA. Glycine is not considered along with these ligands since it is a bidentate ligand. The linear plot observed in the case of IMDA, NTA and EDTA suggests that they possibly form the same number of rings in the chelate. The results of Irving

and Da Silva¹⁴ for the beryllium complexes with uramildiacetic acids are shown by plot 2 in the same figure which lies much above the one obtained for $\log K'_1$ of the ligands mentioned above. Uramildiacetic acid is expected to function at least as a tetradentate. In view of the empirical nature of this correlation, it can only be assumed that NTA and EDTA are also functioning as tridentates on par with IMDA, although they are tetradentate and hexadentate respectively.

2. *Magnesium complexes*: The titration data for these systems are given in Table 3 and the stability

Fig. 1. Correlation of stability of beryllium complexes with basicity of ligands.

1. Results of the present work.
2. Irving's data on Uramildiacetic acids.

TABLE 3—pH TITRATION DATA ON MAGNESIUM SYSTEMS.

		Temperature = 35°, Ionic strength = 0.1 M								
Glycine		$T_L = 5 \times 10^{-2} M$				$T_M = 1 \times 10^{-2} M$				
pH		9.00	9.10	9.20	9.30	9.40	9.50	9.60		
\bar{n}		0.26	0.20	0.25	0.30	0.25	0.25	0.26		
pL		1.87	1.77	1.66	1.58	1.47	1.37	1.27		
IMDA		$T_M = T_L = 1 \times 10^{-2} M$								
pH		7.8	8.0	8.3	8.4	8.7	9.0	9.2		
\bar{n}		0.23	0.30	0.43	0.51	0.64	0.78	0.84		
pL		3.87	3.71	3.50	3.47	3.30	3.21	3.17		
NTA		$T_L = 1.01 \times 10^{-3} M$				$T_M = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$				
pH		6.46	6.85	7.20	8.02	8.59	9.23			
\bar{n}		0.06	0.19	0.33	0.63	0.72	0.78			
pL		6.29	5.97	5.69	5.14	4.71	4.27			
EDTA		$T_L = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$				$T_M = 1 \times 10^{-2} M$				
Volume		0.0	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.65	0.70	0.75	
α		0.0	0.29	0.59	1.18	1.74	1.88	2.03	2.17	
pH		2.95	3.03	3.13	3.41	4.12	4.47	4.69	4.84	
Volume		0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.15	1.2	1.25	1.3	1.4
α		2.32	2.61	2.93	3.29	3.37	3.48	3.62	3.77	4.05
pH		4.96	5.16	5.36	5.60	5.75	5.94	6.31	8.35	10.11

DAS & RAO : THE STABILITY OF BERYLLIUM COMPLEXES WITH ORGANIC LIGANDS

constants of magnesium complexes are given in Table 5. These are, in general, in good agreement with those reported in literature⁴.

3. *Aluminium complexes* : The titration data for the complexes of aluminium are given in table 4 and the stability constants are given in table 5. The low concentrations of aluminium used and the *pH* ranges utilised for calculations exclude the error due to hydrolysis. The value of the stability constant of Al-IMDA complex agrees well with that reported in literature¹⁵.

It may be seen that the stability constants of aluminium complexes increases from glycine to EDTA. The increase in stability is expected from the increase in the number of coordinating groups in the ligands. Comparing the stability constants of aluminium complexes with the corresponding beryllium complexes, it is observed that the stability constants of the former are always higher. Similarly, the difference between the stability constants as one goes from one ligand to the other is more in the case of aluminium than that found in the case of

TABLE 4—*pH* TITRATION DATA ON ALUMINIUM SYSTEMS.

Temperature = 35°, Ionic strength = 0.1 *M*.

Glycine	$T_L = 5 \times 10^{-3}M$				$T_M = 1 \times 10^{-3}M$					
<i>pH</i>	4.25	4.3	4.35	4.4	4.50					
\bar{n}	0.35	0.70	0.89	1.26	1.42					
<i>pL</i>	7.82	7.80	7.77	7.74	7.68					
IMDA	$T_L = 2 \times 10^{-3}M$				$T_M = 1 \times 10^{-3}M$					
<i>pH</i>	3.2	3.25	3.32	3.485	3.651	3.695	3.84	4.04		
\bar{n}	0.29	0.35	0.45	0.59	0.74	0.78	0.93	1.16		
<i>pL</i>	8.85	8.79	8.74	8.58	8.46	8.45	8.31	8.21		
<i>pH</i>	4.2	4.365	4.48							
\bar{n}	1.35	1.55	1.72							
<i>pL</i>	8.14	8.16	8.22							
NTA	$T_L = 1.01 \times 10^{-2}M$				$T_M = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$					
<i>pH</i>	2.72	2.845	3.02	3.14	3.21	3.29	3.40	3.55	3.745	4.06
\bar{n}	0.46	0.57	0.68	0.75	0.79	0.83	0.87	0.89	0.94	0.99
<i>pL</i>	10.26	10.23	10.19	10.16	10.16	10.17	10.15	10.09	10.11	10.39
EDTA	$T_L = 1 \times 10^{-3}M$				$T_M = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$					
Volume	0.0	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.15
<i>a</i>	0.0	0.58	1.16	1.74	2.03	2.32	2.61	2.89	3.18	3.30
<i>pH</i>	2.58	2.65	2.74	2.85	2.91	2.99	3.08	3.20	3.36	3.46
Volume	1.20	1.25	1.3	1.35	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.8	
<i>a</i>	3.47	3.62	3.76	3.91	4.05	4.34	4.63	4.92	5.21	
<i>pH</i>	3.59	3.80	4.13	4.73	5.20	5.78	6.31	7.58	9.03	

TABLE 5—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BERYLLIUM, MAGNESIUM AND ALUMINIUM COMPLEXES AT 35° AND AN IONIC STRENGTH 0.1 *M*

Ligand	Be ²⁺		Mg ²⁺	Al ³⁺
	log <i>K</i> ₁	log <i>K</i> ' ₁	log <i>K</i> ₁	log <i>K</i> ₁
Glycine	6.7	6.4	1.4	7.8
	—	—	2.23(4)	—
IMDA	7.2	6.4	3.6	8.7
	—	—	3.66(4)	8.1(15)
NTA	8.3	6.9	5.4	10.4
	7.11(3)	—	5.41(4)	9.5(3)
EDTA	10.2	9.9	8.4	14.3
	9.3(3)	—	8.9(4)	16.1(4)

The values given in the second line are the results available in literature.

beryllium complexes. This may be attributed to the higher charge and also the higher coordination number of aluminium.

The results of the present study show that the stability constants of the complexes of beryllium, magnesium and aluminium with glycine, IMDA, NTA and EDTA increase as Mg²⁺ < Be²⁺ < Al³⁺ for all the ligands. This is consistent with the *Z*²/*r* values for these metal ions

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to Dr. J. Shankar, Head, Chemistry Division for encouragement and keen interest during the course of this work.

References

1. P. CHARAN DAS and G. S. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (communicated).
2. D. G. PERKINS, *Biochem. J.*, 1950, **51**, 487; 1953, **55**, 649; R. M. IZATT, W. C. FERNELIUS and B. P. BLOCK, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 83—The unpublished results of D. Sen were quoted.
3. C. BAMBERGER and F. LAGUNA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **23**, 1067; J. STARY, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1963, **28**, 132; V. V. STAROSTIN, V. I. SPIESYN and G. F. SILINA, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **8**, 336.
4. A. E. MARTELL and L. G. SILLEN, "Stability constants of Metal-ion complexes", The Chemical Society, Special Publication, London, 1964.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green, London, 1961.
6. A. ALBERT and E. P. SERJEANT, "Ionization constants of Acids and Bases", Matheson and Co., Ltd., London, 1962.
7. G. M. NAIR, "Ph.D. Thesis", University of Toronto, 1965.
8. J. N. BUTLER, "Ionic Equilibria", A Mathematical Approach, Addison Wesley Publishing Co., Inc., Reading, 1964.
9. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2904.
10. F. F. CARINI and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 5745, 1953, **75**, 2889, 1952, **74**, 5053.
11. C. E. BAMBERGER and JOSE BOTBOL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 1569.
12. G. SCHWARZENBACH, A. WILLI and R. O. BACH, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1947, **30**, 1303; G. SCHWARZENBACH, H. ACKERMANN and P. RUCKSTUHL, *ibid* 1949, **32**, 1175.
13. T. MOELLER and L. C. THOMPSON, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1962, **24**, 499.
14. H. IRVING and J. J. R. F. DA SILVA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 458.
15. A. LIBERTI and A. NAPOLI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 89.